

Microwave Processing of Crossply Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Composites Using a Tunable Resonant Cavity Technique

J. Wei, J. Jow, J.D. DeLong, M.C. Hawley, and J. Asmussen*
Department of Chemical Engineering
Department of Electrical Engineering*
Michigan State University
East Lansing, MI 48824

Introduction

Incident electromagnetic fields can interact with conductive and nonconductive materials. The fundamental electromagnetic property of nonmagnetic materials for microwave heating is the total material loss factor ϵ_t'' ($\epsilon_t'' = \epsilon'' + \sigma/\omega\epsilon_0$). In general, the total material loss factor consists of two major components: ionic and dipolar contributions. The dipolar contribution is dielectric loss factor ϵ'' due to the motion of dipoles. The ionic contribution is from conductivity σ due to the motion of ions or electrons. The electromagnetic power per unit volume p_m dissipated in nonmagnetic materials is dependent on the angular frequency ω , the total material loss factor, and the square of the electric field strength $|E|$ inside the material as follows.

$$P_m = 1/2 \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon_t'' |E|^2 \quad \text{where } \epsilon_0 \text{ is free-space permittivity}$$

Microwave processing of carbon fiber/epoxy composites has been investigated using multi-mode microwave ovens [1,2]. In these studies, it was reported that processing of unidirectional composites was effective only with the electric field polarized perpendicular to the fiber axes, and processing of crossply laminates was unsuccessful. When crossply carbon fiber/epoxy composites are loaded into commercial multimode microwave ovens, impedance mismatch occurs between the loaded applicator and the external microwave energy source. The field strength can be significantly reduced. The electric field is also disturbed and out of focus. These untunable applicators can not effectively heat the crossply carbon fiber composites or control the heating process.

However, a tunable microwave resonant cavity has been developed and successfully used to efficiently heat materials and control the heating process [3-6]. The use of the tunable cavity allows efficient transfer of energy into a curing carbon fiber composite because of the ability to maintain a standing-wave resonant electromagnetic field through the processing cycle. This is accomplished by slightly tuning the electric field coupling probe depth and the cavity length. The objectives of this paper are to demonstrate the feasibility of microwave curing of crossply carbon fiber composites and to study the effects of the resonant cavity mode on flexural properties of microwave cured crossply composites using a tunable resonant cavity.

Experimental

Cross-ply carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates were made of 24 ply 3" x 3" Hercules As4/3501-6 prepreg tape (about 35 gram). The laminate was surrounded by an adhesive cork dam and stacked with one-ply porous teflon film, six-ply bleeder cloth, and one-ply non-porous release film on each side. This sandwich-type laminate was sealed in a vacuum bag under a pressure of - 25 in Hg and packed between two thick teflon plates. Each laminate package was then processed in a 7" tunable cylindrical microwave cavity at various resonant cavity lengths. The cavity was always adjusted to resonate at

Table 1: Flexural properties of microwave cured 24-crossply AS4/3501-6

Cavity Length (cm)	Cured Laminate Thickness (mm)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)
9.19	4.09 ± 0.04	125.34 ± 18.08	33.93 ± 1.75
9.40	3.99 ± 0.02	685.60 ± 103.90	44.51 ± 1.14
9.47	4.18 ± 0.11	127.92 ± 70.39	26.23 ± 11.05
9.83	4.43 ± 0.14	87.42 ± 52.48	13.96 ± 7.68
9.95	4.35 ± 0.18	724.91 ± 143.73	40.46 ± 4.29
10.08	3.64 ± 0.03	269.30 ± 239.06	43.85 ± 5.04
13.69	4.23 ± 0.17	228.21 ± 50.91	35.74 ± 5.36
13.72	4.39 ± 0.11	189.33 ± 27.15	29.46 ± 5.01
14.13	4.09 ± 0.23	135.54 ± 15.34	31.80 ± 7.43

Table 2: Comparison of flexural properties between microwave cured 24-ply cross and unidirectional AS4/3501-6 composites

Composites	Cavity Length (cm)	Thickness (mm)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (Gpa)	
Crossply	9.40	3.99 ± 0.02	685.6 ± 103.9	44.51 ± 1.14	
	9.95	4.35 ± 0.18	724.9 ± 143.73	40.46 ± 4.29	
Unidirectional*	Parallel	9.46	4.58 ± 0.10	615.5 ± 72.1	30.37 ± 3.71
		9.61	3.87 ± 0.21	415.7 ± 169.2	34.92 ± 11.14
Perpendicular	8.66	3.42 ± 0.14	851.3 ± 208.8	59.30 ± 3.92	
	9.01	3.17 ± 0.04	944.6 ± 183.1	74.52 ± 11.97	
	13.60	3.30 ± 0.13	769.9 ± 76.2	60.89 ± 10.57	

* from ref. [6]

Fig. 1: Temperature/time profiles during microwave curing of 24-ply AS4/3501-6 laminates

2.45 GHz by adjusting the coupling probe and the cavity length. The laminates were oriented with the top ply fiber direction perpendicular to the energy coupling probe. Cure exotherms were performed at a continuous microwave input power density of 2 w/g (input power level about 70 w) for 90 minutes.

Temperatures on the top laminate surface were measured using fluoro optic thermometers. Each microwave cured laminate was cut into four ASTM D790 3-point flexural test coupons. The flexural strength and modulus were determined using an MTS testing machine with a support span of 64.22 mm and a crosshead speed of 0.06 in/min.

Results and Discussion

A microwave tunable resonant cavity has been successfully used to cure crossply carbon fiber composites. Flexural properties of these microwave cured samples are strongly dependent on the resonant cavity length. Each resonant cavity length corresponds to a particular resonant cavity mode with its own electric field strength and pattern. Flexural properties of 24-ply crossply AS4/3501-6 laminates cured at different resonant cavity lengths are listed in Table 1. Crossply samples cured at resonant cavity lengths of 9.40 and 9.95 cm have flexural properties superior to samples cured at other cavity lengths. This is due to the much stronger and uniform electric field in these two modes. Clearly, crossply carbon fiber/epoxy composites can be cured very well using microwaves if an appropriate resonant cavity mode is selected.

These results are also compared with those of unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates cured with the fiber direction either perpendicular or parallel to the coupling probe for the same heating time at a lower input power density of 1 W/g (6) as listed in Table 2. Temperature-time profiles at the top of the crossply and unidirectional laminates are also shown in Fig. 1. Fig.1 indicates that crossply laminates require higher input power density than unidirectional laminates to obtain the similar temperature/time profile. Thickness of 24-crossply coupons is greater than that of perpendicular coupons but comparable with that of parallel ones. It implies that crossply and unidirectional parallel samples are less compact than perpendicular ones. However, the "good" flexural properties of crossply samples are higher than those of unidirectional coupons cured parallel to the coupling probe but lower than those cured perpendicular to the probe. This may be due to the compaction and/or differences in interfacial bonding strength between the fiber and the matrix.

Conclusion

This work demonstrates that microwaves can cure crossply carbon fiber/epoxy composites at a relatively short time and low input power level using the tunable resonant cavity. It also shows that microwave heating strongly depends upon the resonant cavity mode. Further research will be directed toward determination of the electric field pattern governing the "best" heating process and optimization of the curing process.

Acknowledgment

This research was supported by U.S. Army Grant DAAG 46-85-K-0006.

References

1. W.I. Lee and G.S. Springer, J. Composite Materials, 18, p. 357 (1984).
2. W.I. Lee and G.S. Springer, J. Composite Materials, 18, p. 387 (1984).
3. J. Jow, M.C. Hawley, M.C. Finzel, J. Asmussen, H.H. Lin, and B. Manring, IEEE, Microwave Theory and Techniques, 35(12), p. 1435, 1987.
4. J. Jow, M.C. Hawley, M.C. Finzel, and J. Asmussen, Rev. Sci. Instrum., 60 (1), p. 96 (1989)
5. J. Jow, J.D. DeLong, and M.C. Hawley, SAMPE Quarterly, in press, 1989.
6. G.L. Vogel, J. Jow, J.D. DeLong, and M.C. Hawley, to be presented at ASC 4th Technical Conference on Composite Materials, Oct. 3 - 6, 1989.